

CO₂ Transport and Storage directly from a ship: flexible and cost-effective solutions for European offshore storage

Dissemination and Communication Plan 2025 update

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Dissemination level		

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Introduction

This document presents the approach to and a plan of dissemination, education and communication actions. It updates and builds upon D6.6.

An approach to dissemination and communication haven't change since D6.6. A common understanding and joint message to project results have been established and the team managed to deliver a coordinated, consistent and coincidental manner. The approach is presented in chapter 1.

Second chapter presents the list of carried out and planned activities since D6.6 and till the end of the project.

Approach to communicating and disseminating project results

Internal communication in the consortium – rules of internal engagement

The Teams site is the only official repository and should be used for storing both working documents and final releases. This should ensure trackable progress as well as risk mitigation for project progress in case of unforeseen personal issues or personnel changes. Partners are encouraged to work directly from the Teams site as much as possible or at least regularly backup project progress to it.

Project status meetings are organized once a week to ensure project members stay updated on changes and progress. Weekly meetings can also serve as a general assembly if decisions need to be taken. WP / regional leaders need to remember to update the consortia on progress status.

All papers / presentations / communication should be reported in the SharePoint *WP6 Coordination and Dissemination / Dissemination / Dissemination action list.xlsx* as well as saved in the corresponding folder. Please mark the presentations that are not to be distributed further accordingly.

Confidential data (if acquired from industry partners) and tools described in CA's background knowledge that cannot be shared with the consortia should not be uploaded to Teams / SharePoint. A comparable (to Teams / SharePoint) backup solution should be implied to safeguard the progress and avoid data loss. Handling the data is summarised in Data Management Plan.

External communication

Project partners are encouraged to publish the project results together in joint conference / journal publications as well as jointly participate in communication / dissemination events. The activities will be based on the open science approach as stated in the section 1.6 of the proposal:

The following open science practices will be applied in CTS project:

- Peer review publications will be done in journals offering Gold or Green Access (open access)
- Scientific dissemination activities are prioritising events where presentation materials / recordings are openly available after the event, see 2.4 for details.
- Materials (including recordings, where possible) from the events organised by CTS would be made available on the website.
- Summary of project activities and final summary report would be made available on the project website, including description for general public.
- Engagement with end-users and other potential stakeholders is one of key project elements and constitutes activities of the work package 5.

- Public reports are published on both project website and Zenodo group:
https://zenodo.org/communities/cts_cetp/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

Scientific and popular science communication

Scientific and popular science communication constitute majority of project communication activities. Original planning included key scientific events listed below in addition to CETP communication and dissemination activities.

- The annual CO₂GeoNet Open Forum¹ (October 2023, May 2024 and 2025), one of the most relevant CCS dissemination events in Europe, will be one of the privileged events for dissemination of CTS activities in results, taking advantage that several CTS partners are also CO₂GeoNet members.
- GHGT¹ 17, 2024.
- Climit Summit 2025.
- EAGE GET 2024.
- AAPG ERC 2024
- Baltic Carbon Forum¹ 2023, 2024, 2025.
- Trondheim CCS¹ conference 2025
- ACT/CETP workshops (organized regularly to share project status)

Project extension into 2026 brings 5 new events into the possible dissemination possibilities:

- CO₂GeoNet Open Forum 2026, May
- World CCUS conference, 21-25 September
- GHGT-18, 25-29 October
- Baltic CCUS forum, TBA
- GET 2026 02-06 November

Partner responsible for communication / dissemination event need to inform the consortia as soon as possible that a certain action is planned. This is done by:

1. Listing the event in *WP6 Coordination and Dissemination / Dissemination / Dissemination action list.xlsx*.
2. Informing the consortia during the Monday meeting.
3. Uploading the presentation / abstract / paper / etc. draft as soon as possible to *WP6 Coordination and Dissemination / Dissemination* folder.

In case of disagreement on communication measure or content partners will strive to resolve it in a good faith. General Assembly could be called if necessary to take the decision on the dispute.

Finally, as stated in D6.4. a joint per review publication will be prepared and published in 2026.

Educational activities

Being a relatively small and short project, it was deemed unreasonable to prepare own educational courses or schools, rather than continue and establish existing collaborations and partnerships as listed below.

- CTS will collaborate and contribute to MSc level education with CO₂GeoNet Master course carried out by UniRoma and University of Zagreb if topics

¹ Proceedings from the event are available in accordance with Open Science principle.

offered by the project will fit students' interests. MSc program was not announced for 2025 but is expected in 2026.

- The project will provide lectures and, potentially, a workshop to Sotacarbo summer school 2024 and 2025 editions. The school was held in 2024, but not 2025. Contribution can be provided to 2026 edition if it will be held.
- The project will provide teachers for Panarea school 2024 and 2025 editions. Potentially extending to 2026 as well.

End-user engagement

The end-user engagement is generally governed by WP5, with deliverable 5.1 listing key stakeholders. The main approaches will vary from region to region addressing the status and the key challenges in different geographical areas. Common activities include CTS seminars and webinars. In addition, regional activities will include:

- For Portugal: regular meetings with the industry Club setup for Portugal, including APFF; CIMPOR, LUSICAL /LHOIST and Navigator; Meetings with other relevant stakeholders for transport scenarios (including Sines Port Authority, Figueira da Foz Port Authority, Infrastructures de Portugal, and other potential transport relevant institutions; Meeting with the Secretary of Energy to clarification national policies regarding CCUS – Dialogue with decision makers
- For Denmark: Establish contacts with the storage operators. Understand their view on CCS in Denmark. We try to tailor our approach to their strategy. Continue maintaining communication with CCS license operators.
- For Romania: Establishing communication with stakeholders and organization of the stakeholder meetings
- For Ukraine: As of the early stage of CCS development, lack of specific CO2 data and regional focus of the scenario the contact will be initiated with the top-5 largest polluters in the target regions. Additionally, engagement with national and local authorities, ports and potential transport and shipping operators, potentially could be interested in CTS approach, is planned. A Survey developed will be conducted among all stakeholder groups to provide a comprehensive understanding of the sentiments towards CCS prospects.
- For Norway: Establish contacts with identified emitters once first pass scenario is ready and try to establish a functioning network of local emitters interested in CCS technology in general and direct ship injection in particular. Establish and maintain communication with CCS license operators.
- For Baltics: Mainly connected to Baltic CCS forum carried out annually in October.

The end-user communication in 2026 will be coordinated by NORCE as GeoEcoMar was not able to extend its activities to 2026. The focus will be on Norway, Denmark and Portugal – regions continuing project activities in 2026. Other regions will be involved as much as possible.

Project reports

One of the reasons for delaying the D6.6. from June 2024 was that it was found that the project proposal does not include the status of each of deliverable as public or confidential. During the consortia meeting in October 2024 the following was decided:

Deliverables	Title	Status
D1.1	Report on applicability criteria	Public
D1.2	Report on tool update	Public
D2.1	Report on clusters created	Public
D3.1	Techno-economic evaluation report	Partially confidential if using industry data
D3.2	Techno-economic drivers and challenges for direct ship injection including replicability analysis	Public
D3.3	LCA of CTS deployment of two piloting regions	Public
D4.1	Report on conceptual well design.	Public
D4.2	Report on optimization of intermittent injection scenarios.	Public
D5.1	Stakeholder mapping report	May be partially confidential
D5.2.	Stakeholder engagement annual report.	May be partially confidential
D5.3	Stakeholder engagement annual report.	May be partially confidential
D6.1	Report on kick-off meeting. ONLINE	Internal / confidential
D6.2	Report on consortia meeting 1.	Internal / confidential
D6.3	Report on consortia meeting 2.	Internal / confidential
D6.4	Report on consortia meeting 3.	Internal / confidential
D6.5	Report on consortia meeting 4.	Internal / confidential
D6.6	Annual update of project C&D plan, project profile, and website.	Public
D6.7	Annual update of project C&D plan, report on activities taken in previous year.	Public
D6.8	Final C&D	Public

It was decided that the short project frame does not require 5 project meetings, therefore D6.5. was cancelled.

There is no change to the list of the deliverables except for deadline extensions for WP3-5 into 2026 according with plan provided in Amendment to CA.

For deliverables marked as “may be partially confidential” some sections may be available only for the financial agencies and CTS consortia due to utilisation of industrial data, while overall summary will be made public if possible.

All public reports are made available on CTS website and Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/cts_cetp/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest.

Action carried out so far and planned

Carried out in first reporting period in 09.2023 – 10.2024

Date	Event / Journal	Type	Originally planned
26.09.2023	LinkedIn	Video	
02-06.10.2023	Co2GeoNet OpenForum	Presentations	y
11.10.2023	LinkedIn	video	
12-13.10.2023	Baltics CCS Forum	Presentation	y
17.10.2023	Pilot Strategy meeting in Portugal	Presentation	
18.10.2023	LinkedIn	Video	
24-25.10.2023	CETP Conference online	Online	
30.10.2023	LinkedIn	Video	
21.11.2023	LinkedIn	Video	
26.11.2023	Inno-ccus report	Report	
18.12.2023	LinkedIn	Video	
23-25.01.2024	NEXT conference, Bergen	Presentation	
03.02.2024	Publication at "Figueirense" (local newspaper in Figueira da Foz, Portugal) about the Public Engagement where the PilotSTRATGEY subject was presented	News article	
07.02.2024	LinkedIn / teams	Video	
20-24.05.2024	Co2GeoNet OpenForum	Poster	y
28-29.05.2024	AAPG European Regional conference	Poster	
10-14.06.2024	Sotacarbo summer school	Lecture	
26.06.2024	Presentation for "APFF - Administração do Porto da Figueira da Foz, S.A" port authority	Presentation	n
30.06.2024	ENeRG Newsletter	Article on CTS Project	
08.08.2024	Presentation for REN, possible pipeline operator	Presentation	n
16-19.09.2024	7th International Workshop on Offshore Geologic CO2 Storage (organised by IEAGHG, GCCC (Gulf Coast Carbon Center) and The University of Texas at Austin)	Presentation	

27.09.2024	Participation in the European Researchers' Night with the activity "The role of geosciences in the energy transition"				Presentations and Activities
01-04.10.2024	Baltics CCS Forum, project meeting, seminar				Posters y

Planned actions for second reporting period (10.2024 - 12.2025) and status

Date	Event / Journal	Type	Originally planned	Status
21-24.10.2024	GHGT-17	Posters	Y	Poster presented
04-07.11.2024	EAGE GET 2024	Paper	Y	Paper was not accepted
20.11.2024	Romanian stakeholder workshop	Workshop		Carried out
February 2025	Climit summit			Did not participate
March 2025	Consortia meeting and seminar in Portugal		Y	Carried out
May 2025	Co2GeoNet OpenForum		Y	Several posters presented
June 2025	TCCS-12		Y	Presentation, poster
October 2025	Consortia meeting and seminar in Romania			Carried out
October 2025	Baltics Carbon Forum 2025		Y	Presentation, poster
	LinkedIn / YouTube	Videos from presentation and events		Advertising events, posting news and videos

Other activities carried out in second reporting periods (10.2024 - 12.2025)

Date	Event / Journal	Type
3-4. 10.2024	IX International Scientific-Practical Conference "Subsoil Use in Ukraine. Prospects for Investment"	Abstract & Presentation
21-24.10.2024	Fourth regional stakeholder committee in Portugal (PilotSTRATEGY)	Online Presentation
04.12.2024	Meeting with Secil (Cement company), presentation of CTS	Presentation
13.11.2024	NEXUS conference Évora	Poster
10-11.12.2024	Meeting with Navigator (Pulp & Paper company), presentation of CTS	Presentation
14.11.2024	Advances in Carbon Capture Utilization and Storage	Paper

CTS CETP project

Deliverable 6.7

FINAL

24.03.2025	Meeting with CTCV (glass industry)	Online Presentation
27.04-		
02.05.2025	EGU25 General Assembly in Vienna, Austria & Online	Online Presentation
08.05.2025	Meeting with CIMPOR (cement company) on access to transport and the location and system of the capture centre	Oral Presentation
09.05.2025	Project presentation for EERA JP CCS	Presentation
21-23.05.2025	<u>XVI International Scientific and Practical Online Conference “Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency in the 21st Century”</u>	Abstract & Presentation
13.05.2025	WP6 dissemination activity: visit to a school and presentation of ccus technology to high-school students	Oral Presentation
28.05.2025	5th meeting: Regional Stakeholders of the PilotSTRATEGY and CTS project	Online Presentation
29.05.2025	Meeting with Lime sector - Lhoist	Online Presentation
2-5.06.2025	EAGE Annual, Tolouse	Poster and Oral presentation
04.06.2025	WP6 dissemination activity: visit to a school and presentation of ccus technology to high-school students	Oral Presentation
01.08.2025	Stakeholder meetings and consultations. Romania, Portugal	Meeting
25-28.08.2025	IMAGE 2025 AAPG_SPE	Poster
31.08-		
05.09.2025	IAGA/IASPEI Scientific Meeting 2025 https://iaga-iaspei-2025.org/	Presentations
13.09.2025	WP6 dissemination activity: CO ₂ storage off the coast of Figueira da Foz: Come and see for yourself and give your opinion! Small interactive exhibition about an ongoing research project	Small interactive exhibition
22-23.09.2025	CETP Knowledge exchange event 2025, Leipzig	Presentation
24-25.09. 2025	Panarea summer school	Lectures
27.09.2025	European Researchers' Night 2024 "The role of geociencies in the energy transition"	Presentation
09-10.10.2025	EAGE GET 2025	Presentation, Poster
15.10.2025	Meeting between the Portuguese team and Yilport Figueira da Foz. Company responsible for port operations in Figueira da Foz.	Meeting
15.10.2025	Meeting of the Portuguese team with the Portuguese Climate Agency. It provided a general overview of CCS technology in Portugal.	Meeting
30.10.2025	Meeting between the Portuguese team and NEMO Ships - Galp.	Meeting
18.11.2025	SIXTH REGIONAL STAKEHOLDER COMMITTEE MEETING IN PORTUGAL - Figueira da Foz	Meeting
20.11.2025	Meeting between the Portuguese team and the Portuguese Secretary of State for Energy, Dr Jean Paulo Gil Barroca, about CCS technology	Meeting

03-04.12.2025 NPF CCS conference

Presentation

Planned for the third reporting period, 2026.

Date	Event / Journal	Type
18-21.05.2026	Venice Open Forum https://conference2025.co2geonet.com/	Poster / workshop
21-25.Sep.2026	World CCUS. https://wccus.org/ call for abstracts deadline 01.03.2026	Presentation
25-29. Oct.2026	GHGT-18. deadline 19.01.2026	Presentation
02-06.11.2026	GET2026 https://eageget.org/schedule/	Presentation
Nov. 2026	Per review paper with project summary	Per review paper

Visual theme and web presence

No changes in 2025.

Visual theme

A logo and colour scheme were adopted in early autumn 2024 for all communication methods. No changes since D6.6.

Figure 1. Project logo

Figure 2. Project colour scheme codes and Office colour profile

Web presence

The projects web presence is achieved through several platforms:

- Project website is established at: www.cts-cetp.net

Its main goal is to be a platform providing key project information, aggregating video and other dissemination material and holding the main deliverables.

- LinkedIn:

The main goal is dissemination of project materials and events, stakeholders and broader audience engagement.

- Nasjonalt vitenarkiv (<https://nva.sikt.no/> earlier CRISTIN database):

A mandatory database of government supported projects in Norway. Key information is automatically transferred to NORCE project database. The key goal is to be properly represented upon project supported by Norwegian government.

- CETP project database: Common place for all CETP projects. Project coordinator is responsible for uploading and updating required project materials to the database.